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THE IMPACT OF USING THE MULTIMODAL APPROACH IN ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSE COURSES: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the implications of a multimodal approach to teaching EAP courses, with a focus on a private university in Bangladesh, and whether this approach would improve learners' attitudes toward learning English. An effective experiment was designed and presented to two groups of undergraduate learners at the Green University of Bangladesh to measure the impact of multimodal approach in teaching learning of English. To begin, one group of learners was taught English using a traditional approach, whereas the other group was taught English using a multimodal approach in their English for Academic Purpose courses. Total 90 learners from both groups and two instructors of the course 'English for Academic Purpose' in each group took part in this experimental study. The results of this experiment revealed that learners in the English for Academic Purpose course

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prefer to use variety of modes and semiotic resources simultaneously to better grasp a lesson. Based on the participants' suggestions, this study concludes that the multimodal approach is preferable to the conventional technique.

KEYWORDS: Multinomial approach; multimodality in learning; modes; semiotic resources; multimodal text

INTRODUCTION

The teachers of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) in private universities need to focus on implementing various modes. However, they often rush through documents or materials to meet institutional syllabus requirements within a designated timeframe. In the rapidly evolving landscape of education, learners are distancing themselves from traditional approaches. Despite this shift, many instructors in private educational institutions pay insufficient attention to the needs of the new generation. In an effective EAP class, instructors should prioritize spending a significant amount of time on teaching, observing learners, noting their needs, and ultimately finding standardized solutions through the utilization of various modes and the application of blended techniques with diverse semiotic resources. These activities exemplify the Multimodal approach (Marchetti & Cullen, 2016). Despite its time-consuming nature, instructors often overlook the importance of this approach. Furthermore, learners in EAP courses frequently focus on preparing for tests rather than acquiring a deeper understanding of language usage. The Multimodal approach plays a crucial role, yet its implementation is scarce within the classroom, especially in EAP courses offered by private universities in Bangladesh. This scarcity arises from teachers' rough and ambiguous assumptions about this approach, creating a substantial gap in the teaching process.

A multimodal approach offers support to learners in navigating the challenges encountered within the classroom environment. Moreover, through the integration of multimodality, learners can create conducive situations that foster enjoyable and expedited learning experiences. Despite a body of research underscoring the significance of this approach across various educational fields, the educational landscape in Bangladesh, particularly in the

present era, predominantly witnesses the adoption of a singular approach by teachers. This singular approach poses challenges for learners in terms of the learning process. Consequently, the incorporation of multimodality emerges as a beneficial strategy for addressing the diverse array of challenges confronted by English for Academic Purposes (EAP) learners (Marchetti & Cullen, 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

What is Multimodal Approach in Teaching

Multimodality in teaching refers to the interdependence of various communication modes to complete a communicative process (Ting, 2013). The pedagogical approach to multimodal language learning involves utilizing digital technologies to teach or learn a language through texts, images, audios, videos, and multimedia (Lotherington & Jenson, 2011). Kress and van Leeuwen (2001, p.20) define multimodality as the use of multiple semiotic modes in the design of a semiotic product, with a specific emphasis on the combination of these modes. Each modality covers different aspects of phenomena, challenging prior conceptions and providing resources for imagination and critical thinking (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2001). The capability to consume, interpret, and produce multimodal literacies is increasingly significant for academic and social purposes (Jewitt & Kress, 2003; Yi, 2014).

The term ‘multimodality’ commonly describes practices and resources in contemporary digitally mediated literacy, particularly from a social semiotics perspective, where ‘mode’ is viewed as a culturally and socially fashioned resource for representation and communication (Kress, 2003: 45). A multimodal approach is considered a source of modernity and creativity for both teachers and learners, drawing upon visual, audio, and kinesthetic modes to engage learners in the course content (Laadem & Mallahi, 2019). Despite its benefits, the acceptance of multimodality for teaching and learning has been hindered by traditional views of linguistically based literacy and language (Hundley & Holbrook, 2013). Integrating multimodal approaches in ESL teaching has the potential to enhance learners’ autonomy, motivation, and

accommodate various learning styles (Ganapathy & Seetharam, 2016).

To meet the demands of a rapidly changing society, colleges and universities should acknowledge the limitations of traditional English teaching and actively innovate through various effective ways to cultivate talents that align with social development needs (Wu, 2020). Kress, a key contributor to social semiotic multimodal theory, highlights the affordances of different modes in terms of materiality, emphasizing the unique potentials for representation offered by time-based and space-based modes (Kress 2003: 45). Learners perceive multimodal task designs as enjoyable (Korkealehto & Leire, 2019), and the presentation of multiple input sources affects attentional demands and underlying cognitive processes (sánchez, 2022). The integration of technology in education has elevated the standard of educational materials (Esky, 2019).

Multimodality is a burgeoning academic field studied by researchers from diverse disciplines, including linguistics, literature, communication, visual arts, design, media studies, health sciences, engineering, anthropology, jewelry and fashion design, and information technology. Researchers aim to identify challenges and opportunities in using multimodal approaches to pedagogy in diverse and developing contexts, as exemplified by South Africa (Archer & Newfield, 2014).

The current generation of learners, known as Digital Natives, has grown up in a technology-filled environment and is adaptable to changes, being accustomed to ICT language (Prensky, 2001, as cited in Carroll, 2011). Recent case studies on the effects of multimodal literacy have demonstrated substantial learning among learners exposed to a variety of multimodal tasks related to reading and writing (Walsh, 2010).

Implications of Multimodal Approach in Language Teaching

In the realm of language education, the multimodal approach elucidates the significance of employing diverse semiotic resources, utilizing various modes tailored to learners' strategies and needs in different circumstances. This approach has become standard in the 21st century, encompassing four primary methods: visual, auditory, reading and writing, and kinesthetic (VARK). The

multimodal learning style, integrating multiple communication inputs, proves more effective, utilizing various modes to engage learners. This method involves employing multiple modes, which function as distinct learning channels, leveraging senses such as visual and auditory to address challenges and overcome learners' psychological barriers. Multimodality represents a universal and supportive learning approach, catering to diverse learning requirements by employing efficient communication concepts. This involves simultaneous use of text and audio for reading and listening support, captivating learners through images and scenarios, and providing examples for enhanced comprehension. Using these diverse semiotic resources supports learners, emphasizing the adoption of various modes based on learners' different learning capacities or knowledge levels.

Furthermore, multimodal learning contributes to children's proficiency enhancement and skill development. Numerous studies highlight the effectiveness of multimodal learning, particularly in combining text and visuals for improved learning outcomes. This approach creates a positive and conducive learning environment, advocating for individualized pedagogy to ensure every learner's success in concept clarity. Multimodal texts, serving as composite communication figures, embody various modes, resembling multimedia models that employ different components such as vocabulary, pictures, and sounds to enrich learners' knowledge.

In the contemporary era, where technology plays an integral role in daily life, it can be a valuable semiotic resource in the multimodal approach. Technology facilitates easier learning and teaching, making both teachers and learners active participants. Serving as part of multimodal approach's semiotic resources, technology provides materials with up-to-date information, enabling learners to stay abreast of regular changes and updates while stimulating multiple meanings simultaneously.

The multimodal approach acts as a source of creativity within the classroom, fostering creativity for both instructors and learners. It centers on composing a survey and narrating a comprehensive collection of meaning-making assets utilized by instructors in diverse domains and learning contexts,

ensuring the development of technical meaning that demonstrates their incorporation to create meaning. Overall, the multimodal approach enriches the language learning experience and skill development by incorporating diverse materials that empower learners with extensive opportunities for multimodal learning.

How to Apply Multimodal Method in Teaching

The multimodal approach entails the integration of various modes, and its application to language teaching emphasizes the creative combination of text, audio, and image as distinct modes. This integration is aimed at generating meaning and fostering interaction and learning within the classroom context (Marchetti & Cullen, 2016, p.39). Unlike general English courses, English for Academic Purposes (EAP) courses predominantly focus on instructing learners in formal and academic language genres, rather than conventional and social genres (Hamp-Lyons, 2001).

In the 1990s, Western scholars introduced multimodal theory, proposing the use of diverse semiotic resources, such as sound, images, video, animation, motion, color, and facial expressions, to engage learners' senses and enhance learning efficiency (Pan and Zhang, 2020). Leveraging multimodal and multimedia resources can significantly contribute to enhancing multimodal communication practices in English language teaching within higher education (Crawford Camiciottoli and Campoy-Cubillo, 2018). This perspective aligns with the idea that 'knowledge is multimodal, co-constructed, and performed or represented' (Miller, 2007, p. 65).

A multimodal approach in the classroom serves as a wellspring of creativity for both educators and learners. It taps into available visual, audio, and kinesthetic modes and is not contingent on technology, offering a versatile and innovative means of instruction (Marchetti & Cullen, 2015).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research attempts to identify the perceptions of teachers and learners about the implementation of the multimodal approach to examine the impact of using the multimodal approach in EAP courses. Thus this study has the

following three research objectives:

1. To examine the impact of using Multimodal approach in EAP courses on Learners.
2. To find out the usefulness Multimodal approach for teaching and learning English language.
3. To compare instructor's engagement in traditional teaching and multimodal teaching.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study aimed at scrutinizing and assessing the research through the analysis of data gathered from pre-test and post-test surveys, along with an observation checklist. The research design adopted was of a quantitative nature, allowing for the generation of numerical data and empirical insights using statistical and logical techniques.

Research Settings

This experimental investigation was conducted within the classrooms of Green University of Bangladesh. A control group consisting of 45 learners and an experimental group with an equal number were observed during their participation in the “English for Academic Purpose” course, where both traditional and multimodal teaching approaches were employed.

Participants

The study involved a total of 90 undergraduate participants enrolled in the “English for Academic Purpose (EAP-101)” course. As part of the experimental design, both groups underwent a pre-test and post-test, facilitated by a questionnaire. The participants were initially divided into two sections: Section A, comprising 45 learners as the control group, and Section B, consisting of 45 learners as the experimental group. This resulted in a total of 90 participants, all of whom completed both pre-test and post-test survey questionnaires. Additionally, an observation survey spanned three months, involving around 90 learners and two instructors who were observed during classes.

While choosing participants, components such as gender diversity, different

types of personality, aptitude, hobbies, and so on were not taken into consideration for this experimental study. Distribution of participants is given below in detail (Table 1 and 2):

Table 1: Distribution of Pre-Test / Post-Test Participants

Data Collection Techniques	No. of Participants in the Control Group	No. of Participants in the Experimental Group	Total
Pre- test Survey	45	45	90
Post- test Survey	45	45	90

Table 2: Distribution of Participants of observation

Data Elicitation Techniques	No. of Participants in the Control Group		No. of Participants in the Experimental Group		Total	
	Learners	Teacher	Learners	Teacher	Learners	Instructor/Teacher
Observation checklist →	45	1	45	1	90	2

Research Instruments

The researcher developed an instrument based on multimodal activities and teaching-learning practices. The questionnaire statements can be found in the analysis section of this paper.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedure was organized in various ways. Pre-test and post-test data from both participant groups were utilized to assess the distinctions between the two approaches. Additionally, during the application of interventions in both traditional and multimodal classes, observational data were collected through the researcher's presence.

Data Analysis Methods

Quantitative analysis, exclusively involving descriptive and simple statistical methods, was employed for data analysis in this research. The pre-test questionnaire gathered data in the form of multiple-choice questions, and numerical data were analyzed in MS Excel to generate pie charts and graphs. Percentages were then tabulated.

Results from the Experimental Group

The pre-test and post-test questionnaires were administered separately to participants in both the experimental and control groups. A detailed summary of the pre-test and post-test results from the experimental group is provided in Table 3 for reference.

Table 3: Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Experimental Group

Indicators of Assessment	Results							
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
1. Do you feel comfortable in learning English?	Yes		Partially		No		-	
	15%	45%	35%	32%	50%	23%	-	-
2. What type of mode do you prefer in learning English?	Visual and auditorial learning		Kinesthetic learning (constructing physical activity- play a role of a character)		Learning through reading and writing		All of them	
	35%	17%	10%	9%	50%	16%	5%	65%
3. Where do you see your English Language skill level?	Basic		Good		Advance		Need improvement	
	27%	11%	12%	42%	13%	25%	48%	22%

Indicators of Assessment	Results							
4. How can you improve your English Language skill?	Through watching movies		participating in reading and writing contest		Practical implementation		All of them	
	18%	11%	27%	21%	39%	29%	16%	39%
5. Do you know about Multimodality?	Yes		Partially		No			
	11%	46%	26%	38%	63%	16%	-	-
6. What type of significance is using for learning English in your classroom?	Audio and video		Graded books (books that have simple level of language) and articles		Involving technology for better understanding and practical		All of them	
	17%	13%	56%	22%	19%	11%	8%	54%
7. Learning should be in a particular way or in several ways, what do you think?	One way		Several ways		-		-	
	56%	14%	44%	86%	-	-	-	-
8. How can you justify your self as an English Language listener and speaker?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	23%	36%	11%	8%	32%	42%	34%	14%
9. How can you justify your self as an English Language reader and writer?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	22%	32%	13%	8%	39%	51%	21%	9%

10. Is English Language learning enjoyable?	Yes		Partially			No		-
	13%	36%	29%	53%	58%	11%	-	-

The analysis of pre-test and post-test results (Table 3), expressed as percentages, clearly highlights the substantial impact of a multimodal approach on learners. In the pre-test, the experimental group responded to 10 closed-ended questions, including the query, “Do you feel comfortable in learning English?” During the pre-test, 15% indicated comfort, 35% partial comfort, and 50% discomfort. After implementing the multimodal approach, 45% felt comfortable, 32% partially comfortable, and 23% remained uncomfortable.

Regarding the preferred learning mode for English, 35% initially favored visual and auditory learning, 10% kinesthetic, 50% reading and writing, and 5% a combination. Post-test results revealed shifts, with 17% preferring visual and auditory, 9% kinesthetic, 16% reading and writing, and 65% endorsing a blended approach.

Participants were asked to assess their English language skill levels, with 27% describing their skills as basic, 12% as good, 13% as advanced, and 48% needing improvement in the pre-test. Post-test results showed improvements, with 11% at a basic level, 42% at a good level, 25% at an advanced level, and 22% needing improvement.

Preferences for improving English skills included watching movies (18%), participating in reading and writing contests (27%), practical implementation (39%), and a combination of these (16%). Post-test results demonstrated shifts, with 11% favoring movies, 21% contests, 29% practical implementation, and 39% endorsing all options.

Regarding awareness of multimodality, 11% were initially knowledgeable, 26% partially, and 63% unaware. Post-test results indicated an increase in awareness, with 46% knowledgeable, 38% partially, and 16% unaware.

In terms of significance for learning English in the classroom, 17% initially cited audio and video, 56% graded books and articles, 19% technology, and 8% all. Post-test results showed changes, with 13% favoring audio and video, 22% graded books and articles, 11% technology, and 54% endorsing all modes.

Opinions on learning approaches indicated that 56% preferred a one-way approach, while 44% favored a blended technique. Post-test results showed a shift, with 14% supporting a one-way approach and 86% endorsing several approaches.

Participants' self-assessment of English language proficiency in listening and speaking indicated that 23% considered themselves good, 11% bad, 32% average, and 34% needing improvement initially. Post-test result showed improvements, with 36% considering themselves good, 8% bad, 42% average, and 14% needing improvement.

In terms of reading and writing, 27% initially considered themselves good, 13% bad, 39% average, and 21% needing improvement. Post-test results indicated improvements, with 32% considering themselves good, 8% bad, 51% average, and 9% needing improvement.

Regarding the enjoyment of English language learning, 13% initially found it enjoyable, 29% partially enjoyable, and 58% not enjoyable. Post-test results showed increased enjoyment, with 36% finding it enjoyable, 53% partially enjoyable, and 11% not enjoying, mainly among irregular attendees.

In conclusion, the outcomes of the pre and post-tests (Table 3) underscore the preference for the multimodal approach over the traditional one.

Results from the Control Group

The learners in the control group were administered pre-test and post-test questionnaires. A detailed summary of the pre-test and post-test outcomes for the control group is provided in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Control Group

Area of Assessment	Results							
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
1. Do you feel comfortable in learning English?	Yes		Partially		No		-	
	15 %	17%	35%	39%	50%	44%	-	-
2. What type of mode do you prefer in learning English?	Visual and auditorial learning		Kinesthetic learning (constructing physical activity- play a role of a character)		Learning through reading and writing		All of them	
	35 %	32%	10%	15%	50%	46%	5%	7%
3. Where do you see your English Language skill level?	Basic		Good		Advance		Need improvement	
	27 %	22%	12%	14%	13%	13%	48%	51%
4. How can you improve your English Language skill?	Through watching movies		participating in reading and writing contest		Practical implementat ion		All of them	
	18 %	15%	27%	29%	39%	37%	16%	19%
5. Do you know about Multimodality?	Yes		Partially		No			
	11%	13%	26%	27%	63%	60%	-	-

6. What type of significance is using for learning English in your classroom?	Audio and video		Graded books (books that have simple level of language) and articles		Involving technology for better understanding and practical		All of them	
	17%	16%	56%	52%	19%	20%	8%	12%
7. Learning should be in a particular way or in several ways, what do you think?	One way		Several ways		-		-	
	56%	52%	44%	48%	-	-	-	-
8. How can you justify yourself as an English Language listener and speaker?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	23%	25%	11%	8%	32%	39%	34%	28%
9. How can you justify yourself as an English Language reader and writer?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	27%	29%	13%	10%	39%	46%	21%	15%
10. Is English guage learning enjoyable?	Yes		Partially			No		-
	13%	13%	29%	31%	58%	56%	-	-

The identical set of pre-test and post-test questionnaires was administered to the control group, yielding comparable results (Table 4). However, the outcomes for the control group diverged from those of the experimental group. In the pre-test, approximately 15% of learners felt comfortable learning English, which increased marginally to 17% in the post-test. Meanwhile, 35% were partially comfortable in the pre-test, rising to 39% in the post-test. Those not comfortable decreased from 50% in the pre-test to 44% in the post-test, indicating similarities in the control group's pre-test and post-test outcomes

under the traditional approach.

Regarding learning modes, around 35% preferred visual and auditory methods in the pre-test, 10% favored kinesthetic learning, 50% leaned towards reading and writing, and only 5% preferred all modes. Post-test preferences shifted slightly: 32% favored visual and auditory methods, 15% kinesthetic learning, 46% reading and writing, and 7% favored all modes concurrently.

In terms of English language proficiency, 27% claimed basic skills in the pre-test, 12% had good skills, 13% considered themselves advanced, and 48% identified areas for improvement. Post-test responses mirrored these percentages, indicating consistent outcomes.

Responses to the question “How can you improve your English language skill?” revealed that 18% preferred watching movies, 27% advocated participating in reading and writing contests, 39% favored practical implementation, and 16% chose all options. Post-test results aligned with these percentages.

Multimodality awareness in the control group saw a slight increase from 11% in the pre-test to 13% in the post-test, with 26% and 27% knowing it partially, and 63% and 60% having no knowledge in the pre-test and post-test, respectively.

Regarding the significance attributed to learning English, 17% in the pre-test and 16% in the post-test selected audio and video, 56% and 52% chose graded books and articles, 19% in both tests emphasized the involvement of technology, and 8% and 12% indicated the utilization of all options.

A majority (56%) of learners believed one-way learning was effective for acquiring English language skills, while 44% preferred multiple approaches. Post-test responses remained consistent with these proportions.

Self-assessment of language skills revealed that 23% considered themselves good speakers and listeners, 27% good readers and writers, 11% bad at both, 13% bad readers and writers, 32% average, 39% average readers

and writers, and 34% and 21% acknowledged a definite need for improvement. In the post-test, 25% deemed themselves good speakers and listeners, 8% as deficient, 39% at an average level, and 28% indicating a need for improvement.

Regarding enjoyment, 13% of control group learners found learning English enjoyable in both tests, 29% partially enjoyed it in the pre-test, increasing to 31% in the post-test, and 58% in the pre-test and 56% in the post-test expressed a lack of enjoyment. These consistent results failed to demonstrate contradictions between pre-test and post-test outcomes.

Result of the Learners' Observation

In this empirical investigation, the researcher conducts an observational analysis to examine the level of student engagement in the classroom over the entire session. The observations were systematically conducted in both the control and experimental group classrooms during each session. Specific observation criteria were employed to assess the performance of both learners and instructors in these classrooms. The outcomes are presented in the following table (Table 5):

Table 5: Observation checklist of learner's engagement inside the classroom (experimental group & control group)

SL	Observation	Engagement of the learners inside the classroom (checklist)					
		Always		Sometimes		Never	
		Co	ex	co	ex	Co	Ex
1	full attention during session	29%	62%	22%	27%	49%	11%
2	Involving into pair/group discussions	19%	78%	24%	22%	57%	-
3	Asks questions if they have any requirement for better understanding	3%	58%	16%	31%	81%	11%
4	Follows the instructions of the session	11%	81%	32%	12%	57%	7%

5	Self-motivating via using different modes for better understanding	6%	68%	12%	17%	82%	15%
6	Completing the given multimodal task	10%	78%	26%	11%	64%	11%
7	Willing to participate into conversation for information	-	37%	15%	56%	85%	7%
8	Willing to share their own knowledge with others	-	44%	9%	53%	91%	3%
9	Gives and gets feedback	16%	49%	23%	42%	61%	9%
10	Encourages themselves to perform in front of whole class with full of confidence	-	53%	11%	42%	89%	5%

The researcher utilized a meticulously crafted “Engagement of the Learners inside the Classroom Checklist” to make specific key observations throughout each class session, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the context. This checklist not only aided in identifying crucial inquiries but also served as a valuable tool for tracking learner performance within the classroom.

In the control group, approximately 29% of learners consistently paid full attention during sessions, while 62% of learners in the experimental group demonstrated similar attentiveness. Conversely, 27% and 49% of learners in the control group never paid full attention during sessions, compared to 27% and 11% in the experimental group who sometimes or never paid attention, respectively.

Regarding pair/group discussions, a notable disparity existed between the control and experimental groups. In the control group, 19% always, 24% sometimes, and 57% never engaged in discussions. In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated higher involvement, with 78% always and 22% sometimes participating, while none of the learners refrained from group discussions.

When it came to asking questions for better understanding, only 3% of

control group learners consistently inquired, while 81% never asked questions. In the experimental group, 58% always expressed a willingness to ask questions, 31% did so occasionally, and only 11% refrained from asking, predominantly attributed to irregular attendance.

In following instructions, 11% of control group learners always adhered to instructions, whereas a notable 81% of the experimental group demonstrated consistent adherence. In the control group, 32% sometimes followed instructions, and 57% did not, creating a significant gap in learning. Conversely, in the experimental group, 81% always, 12% sometimes, and only 7% never followed instructions in the EAP course classroom. This comparative discussion contributes to the study's outcome.

Results From Instructors' Observation

Teachers in both classroom groups strive to implement their respective approaches effectively to facilitate learning in their unique ways. However, a substantial disparity exists between the teaching methods employed by teachers in each classroom. In this study, the researcher scrutinizes not only the students' learning approaches but also the teaching methodologies employed by teachers, aiming to anticipate the outcomes in each group. The results of the observation checklists, conducted over a three-month period for all classes, are quantified as percentages and presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Observation checklist of Instructors' Teaching Procedure inside the classroom (experimental group & control group)

SL	Criteria/ statement/ learning activities	Level					
		Yes		Partially		No	
		Co	Ex	Co	Ex	Co	Ex
1	Creating scope for brainstorm	19%	64%	21%	36%	60%	-
2	Adding different media	16%	58%	27%	39%	57%	3%
3	Avoiding the monotonous environment with blended learning techniques	13%	65%	24%	27%	63%	8%
4	Constructing multimodal tasks	5%	78%	12%	22%	83%	-

5	Using texts that includes visual concept	8%	69%	17%	25%	75%	6%
6	Teaching concepts through multiple modes	9%	68%	19%	25%	72%	7%
7	Teaching a content using different Semiotic resources	8%	74%	27%	22%	65%	4%
8	Providing feedback through different media	-	55%	14%	42%	86%	13%
9	Letting learners organize their thoughts in flowcharts diagrams or graphs and explain key concepts with illustrations or pictures	-	49%	20%	39%	80%	12%
10	Teaching major concepts repeatedly with the help of modes	-	67%	26%	29%	74%	4%
11	Encouraging group discussions or debates while learning inside the classroom	9%	59%	22%	36%	69%	5%
12	Using body language gesture and sample or models to explain major concepts with real life examples or scenarios	6%	50%	11%	41%	83%	9%
13	Organizing such situation to experiment or implement the application that learners are learning	-	52%	22%	37%	78%	11%
14	Assigning multimedia presentations, projects, or case studies	19%	70%	27%	30%	54%	-
15	Involving visual, aural, reading writing and kinesthetic learning at the same time to provide a clear concept about the content	-	79%	30%	21%	70%	-

DISCUSSION

This study underscores the robust effectiveness of the Multimodal approach in the “English for Academic Purpose” (EAP) classroom, demonstrating its ability to enhance learners’ English language acquisition by improving multiple skills simultaneously through diverse modes and semiotic resources. Survey results highlight the paramount importance of adopting multiple modes, revealing that the Multimodal approach is particularly beneficial for encouraging differently abled learners. The participants, divided into control and experimental groups, demonstrated significant differences in their responses after undergoing the experiment. While the control group, adhering to a traditional approach, exhibited consistent outcomes in their post-test, the experimental group, exposed to the Multimodal approach, showcased remarkable improvements.

The experimental group members exhibited a substantial advancement in their post-test responses compared to their initial questionnaire answers. Notably, learners attributed their positive experiences to the Multimodal approach, citing its use of diverse semiotic resources that facilitated engagement, participation, and knowledge sharing within the classroom. Challenges initially faced by learners, such as apprehension about interacting with instructors and navigating different modes, diminished over time through guidance and self-motivation. The majority of participants advocated for the continued application of the Multimodal approach in the classroom, emphasizing its role in daily knowledge enhancement and the cultivation of confidence in handling diverse linguistic situations.

Furthermore, the study asserts that the Multimodal method aligns well with the current generation’s technological inclinations, leveraging technology as a mode for teaching English. Given the omnipresence of technology in everyday life, the integration of multimodality in EAP classes emerges as an effective strategy for facilitating quicker and more accessible learning experiences.

Observations in the classroom corroborated the positive impact of the Multimodal approach, revealing heightened engagement among learners in the experimental group compared to the relatively disinterested control group. The use of varied semiotic tools inspired enthusiasm, evident through active

participation, completion of multimedia tasks, and increased interaction with the instructor.

However, the study also identified challenges, including a lack of understanding of different semiotic resources, insufficient instructions for reading comprehension, the need for more education on various listening phases, unfamiliarity with operating systems, and occasional technical difficulties during multimodal teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Educational institutions should prioritize the implementation of innovative methods and approaches, breaking free from the monotony of traditional approaches. Embracing the Multimodal approach can contribute significantly to overcoming these challenges.
2. English Teachers should embrace the Multimodal approach by incorporating blended techniques and modes into their teaching methods, fostering accelerated learning.
3. Assignments and activities should involve different multimedia elements to enhance engagement and learning outcomes.
4. Institutions of higher learning should implement a robust monitoring system to address any operational requirements and swiftly resolve issues that may arise during the implementation of the Multimodal approach.
5. Universities should incorporate multimedia elements into the classroom setting to better support learners and create dynamic learning environments.
6. Teachers should acknowledge that the multimodal approach involves the development of four major skills—auditory, visual, reading and writing, and kinesthetic (VARK)—and tailor teaching strategies accordingly.
7. Ultimately, the findings underscore the transformative potential of the Multimodal approach in EAP classrooms, with these above recommendations aimed at facilitating its effective integration for enhanced teaching and learning experiences.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the Multimodal approach emerges as a cornerstone in various educational settings, seamlessly integrating diverse semiotic resources and modes. This holistic approach is portrayed as a catalyst for unlocking the complete potential of learners while dismantling psychological barriers that might hinder effective learning. The essay asserts that the applicability of the Multimodal approach extends beyond specific domains, permeating every facet of learning and underscoring its universal relevance.

Moreover, the essay underscores the alignment of the Multimodal approach with the overarching goals and objectives of educational institutions. Recognized as a valuable strategy, this approach is positioned to make significant contributions to the broader mission of education. Central to the discussion is the emphasis on learners actively engaging their cognitive capacities during exercises tailored to the Multimodal approach. This not only accommodates diverse learning styles but also cultivates an environment conducive to focused and concentrated learning experiences.

A critical stance is taken against methods that neglect individual learner needs, particularly within the context of Bangladesh's educational system. This critique highlights the adverse effects of one-size-fits-all approaches, emphasizing the necessity for tailored methodologies to enhance the effectiveness of education in the country. In conclusion, the essay advocates for heightened attention from professional teachers and trainers toward the implementation of diverse approaches, methods, styles, and teaching modalities. This call for adaptability and individualization, especially in the realm of English for Academic Purpose (EAP) classes, underscores a commitment to elevating the educational experience and outcomes for learners in Bangladesh.

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